

SUPPLEMENTAL TABLES

Table S1. Loadings of environmental variables on four multivariate niche axes

Variable	Description	PC1	PC2
bio7 ¹	Temperature Annual Range	0.07	0.06
ndvi	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (Greenness)	-0.28	0.20
bio3 ²	Isothermality	-0.37	-0.11
bio12	Annual Precipitation	-0.18	-0.06
bio1	Annual Mean Temperature	-0.31	-0.11
tree	Tree Cover (%)	-0.33	-0.05
ndvi_std	Seasonality of Greenness	-0.36	0.20
bio19	Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	0.37	0.11
bio15	Precipitation Seasonality	-0.36	-0.34
qscat	Vegetation Water Content & Tree Type	-0.27	0.48
bio17	Precipitation of Driest Quarter	-0.07	-0.69
elevation	Derived from Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Elevation Data	0.27	-0.23
Variance Explained		40.2%	15.3%
Eigenvalue		4.8	1.8

¹ (Bio5 – Bio6)

² (Bio2/Bio7) x 100

Table S2. Native species distribution model performances. Models were chosen based on the highest Continuous Boyce Index value for each species and were then used as calibration to project suitable habitat in southern California (Figure 4).

Species	Feature Class	Regularization Multiplier	Continuous Boyce Index (CBI)
Red-crowned Parrot	Hinge	6	0.910
Lilac-crowned Parrot	Hinge	3.5	0.932